

AN ANALYTICAL STUDY ON CYBERSTALKING WITH SPECIAL EMPHASIS ON INVESTIGATIONS THROUGH THE LENS OF DIGITAL FORENSICS

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INTRODUCTION

It is a universal truth that there can be no society without crime or criminals. Crime and criminality have been omnipresent throughout the ages. Numerous criminologists have offered grandiose justifications for why some individuals are predisposed to engaging in criminal behaviour. Researchers have used biological, psychological, and sociological premises to explain the subtleties of criminality.

Currently, as science and technology have advanced in the globe and affected nearly every aspect of our lives, the convenience that these have created in people's lives have been monumental. Technology has changed the way we as humans live, it changes our understanding of the way things work and changes the way we interact with one another.¹

However, the flipside of the story paints a different picture where the people have to live their lives in a state of paranoia. The major reason that can be attributed for this has been the evolution of the cyberspace into a hunting ground for criminals. The criminal opportunities produced in cyberspace have opened up this whole new category of crime for criminologists to study-cybercrimes.²

Certain crimes that were once only committed in the real world have now migrated to the cyberspace as well. One such cybercrime that has been worryingly developing is cyberstalking. Its rapid move up the crime charts has been an issue of major concern. The ramifications of the same being mainly psychological, it can have physical repercussions as well and has been affecting the populace significantly. According to National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB) data, 1176 cases of cybers talking alone were reported around India in the year 2021.³ This just makes up the number of cases that were reported, however, owing to the nature of the crime, much of the instances go unreported.

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1. P. L. Ramesh, "Impact of Technology in Human Life" 6 Global Journal for Research Analysis 106 (2017).

2. Bradford W. Reynolds, *The Anti-Social Network 2* (LFB Scholarly Publishing LLC, 2012).

3. National Crime Records Bureau, "Crime in India 2021" 790 (2022).

Cyberstalking, just like any other cybercrime presents the Criminal Justice System (CJS) with multitude of challenges, especially in matters of investigation. This is mainly because of the ever-evolving nature of technology as well as the anonymity it secures for the users. Investigation of cyberstalking requires a different strategy from traditional stalking, and here is where the Forensic Sciences have stepped in with their newfound species, Digital Forensics.

As the Internet is growing, numerous legal issues have been arising.⁴ The Information Technology Act of 2000 was enacted in response to the need to create a specific regulation on the issue of cybercrimes. Additionally, the Indian Penal Code (IPC), 1860 comes into play in circumstances where some cybercrimes have traits and components alike with traditional crimes, such as stalking and cyberstalking. A thorough examination of the complexities of this crime and its corollaries will paint a picture of the specifics of the investigations as a whole.

II. Offline Stalking versus Cyber Stalking

While cyberstalking is as recent a phenomenon as the internet itself, even offline stalking is a relatively new crime.⁵ Fundamentally, cyberstalking does not differ from offline/proximal stalking, as the ingredients of both are very much alike, however, there are slight variations between the two.

One of the major elements that categorises an act as stalking is that it should create an apprehension of fear or distress in the victim's mind regarding his/her own physical or mental health. This mandates a measure of proximity between the offender and the victim. On the other hand, because the cyberstalkers are not physically present around the victims like that in offline stalking, there are times when the victims are not even aware of or alarmed by the threat lurking over them. Furthermore, it demonstrates that unlike victims of offline stalking, victims of cyberstalking are less likely to be familiar with their stalkers.⁶ It's worth noting that just because cyberstalking does not include physical contact does not mean it's less dangerous.⁷

Cyberspace is a place without bounds. It's a limitless space with abundance of scope for cyberstalkers. Instant messaging, chat rooms, social media networks and even online gaming

4. Rajarshi Rai Choudhury, Somnath Basak & Digbijay Guha, "Cyber Crimes- Challenges & Solutions" 4 International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technologies 729 (2013).

5. Naomi Harlin Goodno, "Cyberstalking, a New Crime: Evaluating the Effectiveness of Current State and Federal Laws" Missouri Law Review 127 (2007).

6. *Supra* note 2 at 10.

7. Fighter Law, *available* at: <https://www.fighterlaw.com/whats-the-difference-between-stalking-and-cyberstalking/> (visited on March 08, 2023).

platforms can be and are being used by the cyberstalkers. It is an established fact that offline stalking comparatively originated earlier than cyberstalking, yet due to the nature of cyberspace, there are more instances of cyberstalking.

Cyberstalking being committed online has a wider reach than offlines talking. For example, an offline stalker may harass the victim by repeatedly telephoning the victim.⁸ But each call is a separate event that takes the stalker's effort and time. This behaviour can easily snowball online because, with only one action, the stalker can create a harassing e-mail message that the computer systematically and repeatedly sends to the victim thousands upon thousands of times.⁹ Anonymity is a trait that is inherent in all of the cybercrimes and as such the stalker being anonymous is much greater a possibility in cyberstalking than in offline stalking. A growing number of online criminals are purchasing software that allows them to stay anonymous while committing crimes on the dark web,¹⁰ the untraceable, encrypted portion of the internet. It presents a rather difficult terrain for the investigators to identify and nab the culprits which is comparatively swifter in cases of offline stalking.

Also, offline stalking events consume a considerable amount of time as compared to cyberstalking, because one can use the cyberspace in a very fluent and swift manner and also the ease of use and access is very much inherent in it. The human effort in cyberstalking unlike any of the traditional criminal cases is very minimal which makes it more convenient to commit than offline stalking.

III. Analysis of Cyber Stalking

As has been defined earlier, in simple terms, cyberstalking is the commission of stalking using Information and Communications Technology (ICT). Though a case of cyberstalking begins in the cyber world, it can eventually have repercussions on the offender-victim relationship in the physical world.

The connotation provided for it under Section 354D IPC talks about “any person monitoring the use by a woman of the internet, email or any other form of electronic examples to communication.”¹¹ The phrase "any other form of electronic communication" in this case gives the clause a broad meaning. In fact, it closes all gaps that might arise in the future because it is

8. *Supra* note 5 at 129.

9. *Ibid.*

10. As defined by Kaspersky, the dark web is the hidden collective of internet sites only accessible by a specialized web browser. It is used for keeping internet activity anonymous and private, which can be helpful in both legal and illegal applications

11. Indian Penal Code, 1860 (Act 45 of 1860), s. 354D.

impossible to streamline just a few devices or platforms via which cyberstalking might occur given the rapid advancement of technology. The aforementioned provision is somewhat limiting because it completely dismisses the possibility that men could also become victims of cyberstalking. Mumbai-based entrepreneur Vijay Nair being cyber stalked by a woman is a landmark example of the same.¹²

Cyberstalking involves a series of behaviours and actions over a period of time that are intended to intimidate, alarm, frighten, or harass the victim and/or the victim's family, partner, and friends.¹³ These behaviours and actions include (but are not limited to): flooding the user's inbox with emails; frequently posting on the user's online sites, pages, and social media accounts; repeatedly calling and/or texting the victim, leaving voicemails, and sending follower and friend requests; joining all online groups and communities the victim is a part of or following the victim's posts through acquaintances, colleagues, classmates, family members' or friends' social media accounts; and continuously viewing the victim's page.¹⁴ In both online and offline settings, offenders have the ability to continuously watch, observe, and monitor victims with or without the victims' knowledge.

The nature of cyberstalking reveals that it is difficult to combat because the stalker could be in another state or sitting three cubicles away from the victim.¹⁵ Online anonymity can make it difficult to verify a stalker's identity, collect the necessary evidence for an arrest and then trace the cyberstalker to a physical location.¹⁶

There can be many reasons for which a perpetrator may cyberstalk someone. Harassment is one of the primary reasons and has an aggravated form in the guise of revenge. Harassment can primarily be attributed to some kind of sadistic pleasure of an offender. Sometimes for acts of revenge because of failed love proposals or the termination of a relationship or a marriage, cyberstalking maybe carried out. Also, there are cases of one-sided love or fascination of one person towards the other which might lead to cyberstalking. It is worth mentioning that, people who are currently in a relationship or in a marital bond also undertake cyberstalking because of curiosity or trust-issues over their partners.

12. The Times of India, available at: <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/delhi/cyberstalking-law-ill-equipped-to-protect-women-non-existent-for-men/articleshow/59179132.cms> (visited on June 5, 2023).

13. UNODC, available at: <https://www.unodc.org> (last visited on June 25, 2022 at 09:00 am).

14. *Ibid.*

15. Privacy Rights Clearing house, available at: <https://privacyrights.org> (visited on June 25, 2022).

16. *Ibid.*

Characteristic	Share of Respondents
Checked their phone to view text messages, phone calls, direct messages (DMs), emails, or photos	17%
Reviewing their search history on one of their devices	13%
Used knowledge of their passwords to access their device or online accounts	10%
Tracked their location via a location sharing app	9%
Created a fake profile to check on them on social media	8%
Used an app to monitor their text messages, phone calls, direct messages (DMs), emails, or photos	7%
Tracked their physical activity via their phone or health app	6%
Created a fake profile on a dating app to see if they have a dating profile	6%
None of these	63%

Table.1: Most common forms of cyberstalking an ex or current partner worldwide from November 15 to December 7, 2021.¹⁷

The above data is based on a survey conducted on a global scale between November 15 to December 7, 2021 and it reveals the most common ways that are employed by perpetrators to cyberstalk an ex or a current partner. The ways of cyberstalking mentioned herein are not exhaustive. The data reveals that cyberstalking is more common amongst people who have a connection, and the perpetrator has direct access to the victim's social devices or platforms.

17. Statista, *available* at: <https://www.statista.com> (visited on June 28, 2022).

IV. Mens Rea/Actus Reus in Cyberstalking

The architecture of social networking sites presents a very complicated picture in cybercrime jurisprudence. As has been discussed throughout the paper, cyber space is a limitless terrain without any bounds. It complicates matters for the CJS to operate especially in cases of cyberstalking.

For committing a crime, the intention and act both are taken to be the constituents of the crime, which is embedded in the maxim "*actus non facit reum nisi mens sit rea.*"¹⁸ It means that, generally, a person cannot be guilty of a crime unless two elements are present: the *actus reus* (guilty act) and the *mens rea* (guilty mind).¹⁹ It applies in cases of cybercrime as well. As for example, in an instance of hacking, the act of the perpetrator in illegally intruding the domain of some other person and siphoning off valuables makes up for the *actus reus*. And the knowledge of the perpetrator that the access to the particular space is illegal draws up the *mens rea*.

However, to prove both these elements in case of cybers talking is somewhat complex. The whole idea behind social networking sites is the creation of social connections with people who are already known as well as with those that are unknown. The algorithm of such sites is tweaked in such a way that they make recommendations to connect based on varied parameters. For example, Instagram presents to the users a tab named 'Suggested for you' under which a user may find account suggestions of different people who might be mutual friends with someone who the user might already be connected with in the platform. This lures the user into the unknown space of a different user, which he might exploit in different ways.

Despite any platform's claims of privacy protections such as private profiles and turning off account suggestions, etc., it raises concerns about the authenticity of the sites in terms of cybers talking because it gives potential stalkers a place to continue their operations unhindered. Also, shutting down the safeguards means the user being devoid of fascinating stuff to relish on the platform.

In these situations, it can be difficult to demonstrate *mens rea* and *actus reus* because the stalker may routinely observe the everyday activities of a person who frequently posts updates in the platform without him/her having any whiff about being stalked. It does not create any

18. State of Rajasthan v. Shera Ram alias Vishnu Dutta, Criminal Appeal No. 1502 of 2005.

19. Oxford Reference, *available* at:

<https://www.oxfordreference.com/display/10.1093/oi/authority.20110803095349253;jsessionid=5F9C5ECAD A7FB93E47913A48A52428D2> (last visited on March 09, 2023 at 01:41 pm).

apprehension of fear or disturbance like that in offline stalking cases. For the reason, that the platform itself is providing an avenue, to question the legitimacy of the action on the part of the person would be wrong. And also, this does not imply that the platform is liable as it is providing safeguards.

Actus reus in such cases is the act of the stalker in invading the personal space of some other person and the *mens rea* should have been the knowledge on the part of the stalker that such an invasion is not appreciated. The lament of *actus reus* gets nullified by the fact that the idea behind social networking is to check out profiles and connect and also there is no bar to the number of times a person can actually do so. *Mens rea* on the other hand, in many instances is difficult to judge, again because of the sole nature of social networking. To say that the intent was malicious or wrongful would be vague as such. These factors as such complicate the jurisprudential aspects of cybercrime.

V. Catalysts and Impact of Cyberstalking

The inception of the smartphone was a boost to the entire domain of ICT. These have a strong resemblance with computers in terms of functionality, but the aspect of mobility bolsters its utility. These have exacerbated the serious effects of cyberstalking. Latest technologies like the Global Positioning System (GPS) being infused with the smartphones can allow cyberstalkers to gain information about the location of their targets.

The rise of social media has also had an impact on the rising number of cyberstalking cases. People can now create social relationships online through a variety of sites. On the other hand, regular updates about a person's everyday life and activities are like inadvertently asking cyberstalkers to track his/her every step.

A profile on a social network might include information such as the owner's email address, phone number, general (or even specific) address information, birthday, legal name and even names of family members.²⁰ If a victim has a public profile, a stalker could easily access any information posted to the social networking account.²¹ Check-ins at restaurants or cafes on Facebook, exposing the exact location at one point in time, are a pretty typical occurrence these days.

20. *Supra* note 15.

21. *Ibid.*

Cyberstalking can have significant psychosocial impacts on the victims.²² They report several severe consequences of victimization: Increased suicidal ideation, fear, anger, depression, and Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD).²³ The personal, professional and social life of the victim can get highly affected.

Also, there are instances where a large number of cyberstalking cases go unreported because of the fear of further victimization. Most often the cyberstalkers target people who they are familiar with. Both the victim and the perpetrator may belong to a common social circle. Also, there are no bounds to the use of social media and as such there are endless possibilities for a perpetrator to randomly target anyone.

Fig.1: Statistics on Cyber Stalking/Cyber Bullying of Women (Sec.354D IPC r/w IT Act).²⁴

The statistics above represent the growing graph of cyberstalking incidents in India over a five-year period between 2017-2021 as per the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB) data. A reason for the rise in numbers can be attributed but not limited to the pandemic. The COVID-19 pandemic and the eventual lockdowns mandated the use of ICT technology for day-to-day work, there by increasing the online presence of people to a far greater extent. This in turn opened up avenues for the cybercriminals. The repercussions of the pandemic led to the increased online presence which is still very evident.

22. National Library of Medicine, available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov> (visited on June 25, 2022).

23. *Ibid.*

24. National Crime Records Bureau, available at: <https://ncrb.gov.in> (visited on June 15, 2022).

VI. Legal Framework

The Information Technology (IT) Act, 2000 was passed in order to fill the lacunae created by the development of technology and the eventual emergence of cybercrime in the nation. The primary and most important law pertaining to criminal activities in India is the Indian Penal Code (IPC), which was passed in 1860. Therefore, there may occasionally be a contradiction in how the requirements of the two pieces of legislation are applied in particular situations. The principle to be applied in such scenarios is that special laws would take precedence over ordinary laws in these situations, and later laws would take precedence over earlier legislation.²⁵ Therefore, the IT Act shall supersede the IPC in cases of conflict.

However, the IT Act does not specifically incorporate the aspect of cyberstalking per se. The Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013 introduced to the IPC, Section 354D giving a situational picture as to what constitutes cyberstalking. But it does not use the term 'cyberstalking' specifically. Also, the provision has been criticised of not being gender neutral and being more centred towards women.

There are other provisions in the IPC like Section 292 which makes it punishable, the conveyance of any obscene material over the internet to deprave the receiver, Section 507 which deals with criminal intimidation through anonymous communication and Section 509 which can be attracted if the offender's actions violate the privacy of a women or infringes the modesty of a women.

The striking down of Section 66A by the Supreme Court from the IT Act in the case of *Shreya Singhal v. Union of India*²⁶ in 2015 pertaining to punishment for sending offensive messages through communication service, etc has left a void as regards cyberstalking in the IT Act. However, Section 67 explicitly makes it punishable to publish or transmit any obscene material in the electronic form. Sections 67A and 67B respectively deals with publication and transmission of sexually explicit material in electronic form and the publication and transmission of material depicting children in sexually explicit act in electronic form including facilitating abuse of children online. Therefore, only if a cyberstalker publishes obscene matter a case can be filed against him under the provisions of the IT Act.

25. *Sharat Babu Digumarti v. Government of NCT of Delhi*, AIR 2017 SC 150.

26. AIR 2015 SC. 1523.

VII. Investigations

Investigation of cyberstalking poses new challenges to the CJS because of a wide variety of reasons. The element of anonymity in these cases is very high. Even a perpetrator who is not that adept in cyberstalking can remain anonymous because that is how the online environment is. It can be committed from anywhere without coming into close physical proximity with the victim. Whenever a cybercrime takes place, the police are the first-responders. However, for the collection and handling of the evidence and other scientific assessments of the crime, the assistance of forensic experts is called upon, more specifically the Digital Forensic experts.

The use of advanced technologies to commit cyberstalking raises significant investigative and evidentiary challenges.²⁷ The evidence that is collected from such cases can be very volatile and like any other electronic evidence needs special expertise to handle. Unlike general physical evidence in traditional crimes that can be photographed, video captured or sketched, the handling of digital evidence is somewhat complex. There might be occasions where the perpetrator might program the device used for cyberstalking to automatically erase all the data which would make it difficult to retrieve the same.

Section 80 of the Information Technology Act, 2000 provides that notwithstanding anything contained in the Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973, any police officer, not below the rank of a Deputy Superintendent of Police, or any other officer of the Central Government or a State Government authorised by the Central Government in this behalf may enter any public place and search and arrest without warrant any person found there in who is reasonably suspected or having committed or of committing or of being about to commit any offence under this Act.²⁸ Though the Information Technology Act, 2000 does not define cyberstalking per se, but it anyhow falls under the scope of the Act.

Crime detection falls into three distinguishable phases: the discovery that a crime has been committed, the identification of a suspect, and the collection of sufficient evidence to indict the suspect before a court.²⁹ The primary responsibility for this falls with police and as such the investigating officer will employ all means to quiz all those who might be suspected to have some kind of connection with the crime as well as the witnesses. The complainant or the victim shall be interviewed to find out intricate details about whether she has any knowledge as regards

27. Science Direct, *available* at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com> (visited on June 25, 2022).

28. Information Technology Act, 2000, (Act 21 of 2000).

29. Britannica, *available* at: <https://www.britannica.com> (visited on June 26, 2022).

who the offender might be, any reason for which she might have been targeted, when did she realize that she was being cyberstalked and what kind of ways and platforms were employed by the cyberstalker.

The timeline of events shall be sought to be reconstructed based on all the available details. The evidence and the materials found shall assist in the recreation of the events. Therefore, the investigating officer shall do everything to secure any possible digital or physical evidence available therein. As has been mentioned earlier, Digital Forensics is the process of uncovering and interpreting electronic data.³⁰ The goal of the process is to preserve any evidence in its most original form while performing a structured investigation by collecting, identifying and validating the digital information for the purpose of reconstructing past events.³¹

The first step of the forensic investigation entails identification of the probable sources of evidence. It can be a laptop, a smartphone, external hard disk drive or any other device which was used for the commission of the act or maybe it belonged to the victim. Second, preserving the identified data by protecting it from being contaminated or lost is carried out. It is basically securing whatever is contained within a device. In cyberstalking cases, for example, preserving a smartphone can be very crucial. The act of cyberstalking might have been done using a messenger application on the phone but it being a wireless device there is all possibility of wirelessly corrupting the evidence therein. In such cases Faraday bags are used for its preservation. It protects electronics from being damaged by radio frequency interference (RFI) or from an electromagnetic pulse (EMP) by not allowing radio frequency or electromagnetic pulse waves to pass through the material.³²

After preservation, the requisite information or data is extracted from the device. It can be done by printing or copying the contents to some other device. Various data retrieval softwares are available. Some are open-source while some are paid services. The choice of software depends on the type of data to be retrieved, because there might be occasions where the data might be highly encrypted and there might be times where there is null encryption. The data so retrieved shall then be analysed with apt procedures and finally a report on the findings and all other relevant details shall be prepared which can be presented before the court.

30. Techopedia, *available* at: <https://www.techopedia.com> (visited on June 26, 2022).

31. *Ibid.*

32. Privacy Pros, *available* at: <https://privacypros.io> (visited on June 26, 2022).

Digital footprints become very crucial in cyberstalking investigations. It is the information about a particular person that exists on the Internet as a result of his/her online activity.³³ As for example, the browser history of the offender might reveal a lot of details as regards his activities. These can be deleted by the offender which is impossible for a layman to retrieve, but the forensic experts can methodically do so. An active digital footprint is intentional and purposeful, that is, data left on the internet because it was intended.³⁴ Likewise, passive digital footprint is created by unintentional data- the data left behind without meaning to, or without having a choice to.³⁵

The principle described by Dr Edmond Locard, more commonly known as the Locard's Exchange Principle, that when two objects come into contact with each other something is exchanged and taken away by both objects applies to any criminal act and is true for cybercrimes as well.³⁶ This is the basis of the transfer and recovery of all scientific evidence.³⁷ However, the contact between the offender and the victim in cyberstalking cases is in the binary form or so as to say, it is virtual.

From a judicial point of view, the opinion of a digital forensic expert becomes relevant under Section 45A of the Indian Evidence Act, 1872. It says that when in a proceeding, the court has to form an opinion on any matter relating to any information transmitted or stored in any computer resource or any other electronic or digital form, the opinion of the Examiner of Electronic Evidence is a relevant fact.³⁸

VIII. Challenges in Cyberstalking Investigations

Some of the key challenges in conducting digital forensics investigations related to cyberstalking can be summarised as under:

1. **Anonymous Perpetrators:** Cyberstalkers frequently go to considerable efforts to hide their identity, employing strategies like proxy servers, VPNs, and anonymous email accounts. It might be quite difficult to discover who an

33. EdTech Review, *available* at: <https://www.edtechreview.in/dictionary/what-is-digital-footprint/> (visited on June 26, 2022),

34. Business Insider, *available* at: <https://www.businessinsider.com/guides/tech/what-is-a-digital-footprint?IR=T#:~:text=Your%20digital%20footprint%20refers%20to,behind%2C%20like%20your%20IP%20address> (visited on June 26, 2022).

35. *Ibid.*

36. Oxford Reference, *available* at: <https://www.oxfordreference.com/> (last visited on June 26, 2022 at 08:45 pm).

37. *Ibid.*

38. Indian Evidence Act, 1872, (Act 10 of 2009).

anonymous cyberstalker is.

2. **Cross-Jurisdictional Issues:** Cyberstalking cases often involve perpetrators and victims in different jurisdictions or countries. Investigating and prosecuting across borders can be complex due to varying laws and challenges in obtaining evidence from foreign entities.
3. **Digital Evidence Preservation:** Digital evidence must be gathered and preserved, but it can be challenging to assure its integrity, especially if the offender has the technical know-how to hide their trails or erase evidence.
4. **Encryption and Anonymization:** Cyberstalking messages and actions are difficult to intercept and decode due to encrypted communications and anonymization techniques. Specialized knowledge and equipment may be needed to decode encrypted data.
5. **Data Volume and Complexity:** In today's digital age, the sheer amount of digital data generated might be daunting. It takes a lot of time and resources to analyse huge amounts of data to spot cyberstalking activity.
6. **Ephemeral Data:** On platforms with self-destructing or ephemeral messaging features, cyberstalking is frequently practised. It is difficult to locate and save evidence before it vanishes as a result.
7. **Social Media and Online Platforms:** Social media and online platforms are frequently used by cyberstalkers as harassment tools. Collaboration with service providers is necessary for investigations, and there may be legal repercussions.

IX. CONCLUSION

Cyberstalking is relatively a new form of crime. The hurdles for the law enforcement authorities to track and apprehend cybercriminals applies significantly in these cases. Also, anonymity is a major concern here. With the wide use of internet and rapid development of technology and platforms for social connections, cyberstalking cases are gradually shooting up the charts not only in India, but on a global scale.

Digital Forensics is very much instrumental to the CJS in cases of cyberstalking. The factor of

anonymity of the offenders can be tackled with the tools and techniques employed by the experts. Constant upgradation of the techniques of cybercriminals mandates proportionate upgradation to the tools and techniques of investigations.

The findings of the study can be summarised as under:

1. The adverse impact of the proliferation of technology is very much evident with the rising number of cases of cybercrimes. Social media platforms are major cause of concern in cases of cyberstalking. Though privacy controls are constantly updated, the nature of cyberspace presents amplitude of possibilities for the cyberstalkers.
2. The impact of cyberstalking can be immediate and long-lasting. The mental health and well-being of the victims is deeply impacted. PTSD symptoms can turn-up at any time during the lifetime of a victim.
3. Digital Forensics is an integral element to the domain of the CJS. However, maintenance of a proper set-up with the requisite resources and personnel can be a tolling and costly affair.
4. The nature of digital evidence entails expertise in its handling and it makes Digital Forensics all the more essential. There are major distinctions between digital evidence and physical evidence and as such an expert proficient in Digital Forensics is preferred for collection and analysis of digital evidence.
5. Neither the Information Technology Act, 2000 nor the Indian Penal Code, 1860 specifically defines and prescribes any punishment for cyberstalking. Though the IPC gives a situational depiction of an act of cyberstalking, it does not specifically incorporate the term 'Cyberstalking' as such. Cybercrimes and conventional crimes, though seems alike when the outcome of the crimes is calculated, are very much different altogether. As such, stalking and cyberstalking are also very much distinctive.
6. Section 354D of the IPC specifically considers cyberstalking against women but neglects the fact that men can be victims of the crime as well. Though statistics reveal women are the primary targets, still there are instances where men fall victim to cyberstalking cases.

The following ideas can be taken as suggestions based on the findings of the research work:

1. Shelving the pace at which technology is developing just to curb the growing rates of cybercrimes will be unreasonable and impractical. Therefore, increasing the digital literacy amongst the masses is more preferable. Digital literacy in this case not only entails just the operation of a computer or a smartphone, but it signifies being literate in the security and privacy aspects of the cyberworld.
2. Digital Forensics is a developing subject-matter as well as cybercrimes are dynamic and ever-evolving. Therefore, the infrastructure at play, at times may not be comprehensive enough to deal with newfound and critical situations. Hence, periodic upgradation of the tools and techniques in consonance with international developments should be carried out. Well-equipped laboratories at the district level in each state must be mandatorily maintained. Also, research and development of indigenous methods and techniques should be encouraged.
3. Training programmes for the police or investigating authorities should be conducted on the handling of digital evidence thereby also increasing the manpower. It requires special training and with the current state of affairs whereby majority of the things have been digitalized, in most of the crime scenes there is a strong possibility that the first responders will encounter digital evidence. Collaborations with the Interpol and also initiatives for global or regional alliances should be taken up by the Government as regards this.
4. The Information Technology Act, 2000 should be amended to incorporate cyberstalking in a dedicated sense. The Indian Penal Code, 1860 does not incorporate the term 'cyberstalking' and as such changes should be made in the former law as it is a specialized legislation on information technology and also it supersedes the IPC in matters of conflict.

5. Any penal law should incorporate provisions looking at the bigger picture. As such Section 354D of the IPC excluding men as victims is somewhat debatable. Therefore, necessary alterations should be done to the same.
6. Sensitisation of the public on key cyber safety measures should be undertaken by the police or any other authority. This is highly essential as the modern-day affairs necessitates people to engage more over social media and most often people are themselves responsible for making themselves vulnerable to cyberstalkers.

In view of the above findings and suggestions, it is evident that there is no dearth of laws to address the issue of cybercrimes in India. However, cyberstalking as a specific crime has to be defined and penalized. Also, efforts should be made to prepare a stringent ecosystem whereby people are more proficient in the use of technology having due regard to cyber safety tips and measures. Digital Forensic infrastructure being of paramount importance, focus should be applied on its regular upgradation with state-of-the-art facilities, tools and techniques.